

THE INFLUENCE OF CERVIX STIMULATION AND BOAR PRESENCE AT ARTIFICIAL INSEMINATION ON SOWS FERTILITY

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SUMMARY: These study compares farrowing rate and litter size in AI sows after cervix stimulation with catheter or fence-line boar contact around insemination. Within first 7 days after weaning, the total of AI 149 sows were divided into three groups. Group I: cervix stimulation with catheter immediately before and after sperm deposition (n=49), Group II: fence-line boar contact immediately before, within and after insemination (n=50), Group III: not treated, control, sows (n=50). Farrowing rate were significant higher ($P < 0.05$) after cervix stimulation (90%) or stimulation by boar presence (86%), compared with control sows (78%). These values were not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) among the stimulated sows (Group I and II). Performed treatments have no significant effect on litter size. These results indicate that cervix stimulation or boar presence at AI can be useful method to improve sows fertility.

Key words: cervix, boar presence, stimulation, myometrial activity, fertility, sow.

INTRODUCTION

During mating and artificial insemination in sows, semen is deposited intra-cervically. From the site of deposition, sperm cells must be distributed over both horns and transported to the tubal end of the horns, i.e. utero-tubal junction, which serve as a sperm reservoir (Hunter, 1981). The transport of sperm cells through the uterine horns is believed to be a passive process, in which intrinsic sperm cell motility plays no part (Langendijk et al., 2005). This passive transport is probably driven by the flow of intrauterine fluid containing sperm cells, due to gravitational force, movement of the sow and uterine contractions (Scott, 2000). Inadequate stimulation of the sow during and

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after insemination result in reduced myometrial contractions (Langendijk et al., 2002) and a poorer sperm cell transport to the oviduct (Langendijk et al., 2003; Stančić et al., 2006). Inadequate sperm transport within the uterus result in decreasing the sows fertility (Langendijk et al., 2005). It has been shown that inadequate stimulation of sow during and immediately after insemination is the most common factor that influence the sows fertility rate (Spronk et al., 1997).

In farm practice, the reproductive performance of artificial inseminated sows is often lower than that achievable with natural breeding (Spronk et al., 1997; Stančić, 2000). It is often result inadequate myometrial stimulation, due to the small dose volume, high dilution rate of native ejaculate, as well as an inadequate stimulation of the sow by boar presence and absence of mechanical stimulation of the cervix (Langendijk et al., 2003; Beham and Watson, 2005; Kemp et al., 2005; Mezalira et al., 2005; Stančić et al., 2006). An adequate myometrial stimulation is most important in the intrauterine insemination technology with reduced volume and spermatozoa number doses (Roseboom et al., 2004; Mezalira et al., 2005; Stančić et al., 2010).

The aim of the present study was to investigate the effects of cervix stimulation by insemination catheter or by presence of boar around the time of sow insemination, on the farrowing rate and litter size.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted during September to November 2011, in an intensive piggery housing about 1,200 sows. Lactation length of herd was average 28 days. Average sows farrowing rate at the farm in 2010, were 76%, and average liveborn piglets per litter were 10.68. Estrus detection of weaned sows involved full boar contact once daily starting on day 2 after weaning. At detection of the first or repeat estrus, sows were inseminated with 4×10^9 sperm cells in 100 mL dose (BTS-extender, Minitübe, Germany). Insemination was repeated 24 hours later if sows still exhibited estrous behavior, using disposable Safe Blue® AI catheters, lubricated and single wrapped in protective sheaths, sterilized (Minitübe, Germany). Third estrus inseminations were not allowed. Age of semen at insemination was 4-6 hours to 1 day.

At the time of AI (4-5 days after weaning), experimental sows (2 to 5 parity) were assigned to three groups. Group I: stimulation of cervix by moving the top of the catheter within the cervix, about 1 minute before and 1 minute after sperm deposition (n=49), Group II: fence-line boar contact with sow immediately before, within and about 5 minutes after insemination (n=50) or Group III: insemination without cervix stimulation or boar presence, control group (n=50). Data recorded were farrowing rate after first postlactational insemination and subsequent litter size (liveborn, stillborn and total born piglets).

Obtained data were analyzed by using software package Statistica 10 (StataSoft 2012). Data for litter size were testing by General linear model (GLM) and by LSD test. Farrowing rate was analyzed by test of proportion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our results demonstrated that farrowing rate were significant higher ($P<0.05$) in sows with cervix stimulation, group I, (90%) and in sows stimulated with boar presence, group II (86%), compared with unstimulated, control, sows (78%). These value were not significant differ ($P>0.05$) among the stimulated swos (Group I and II). Performed stimulation treatments has no significant effect on litter size (Table 1).

Table 1. Farrowing rate and litter size in treated and control sows (average $\pm$ SD)

		Treatment groups		
		Stimulation method		Control (Group III)
		Cervix by catheter (Group I)	Boar presence (Group II)	
No. of AI sows		49	50	50
Farrowing rate (%)		90% (44/49) ^a	86% (43/50) ^a	78% (39/50) ^b
Av. litter size (n)	Liveborn	11.98 $\pm$ 2.961	11.86 $\pm$ 2.562	11.79 $\pm$ 2.755
	Stillborn	0.66 $\pm$ 0.805	1.25 $\pm$ 1.149	0.77 $\pm$ 0.777
	Total	12.64 $\pm$ 3.170	13.12 $\pm$ 2.932	12.56 $\pm$ 2.780

^{a,b}Within a row, means without common superscripts differ ($P<0.05$).

Values in parenthesis: No. farrowed/No. inseminated.

The establishment the optimal number of spermatozoa in the utero-tubal junction, caudal istmus and the site of fertilization (ampulo-istmic junction of the oviduct) is the key factor for successful ovulated ova fertilization (Hunter, 1981). After deposition in to the cervix, spermatozoa undergoing the passive transport within the uterine horns to the utero-tubal junction. This passive transport is mainly driven by uterine contractions (Scott, 2000) influenced by dramatically oxytocin concentration increases in the blood of sows, within 2 minutes of the onset of ejaculation by a mature boar (Levis, 2000). During and around mating, several sexual stimuli are involved that may be important for their effect on uterine activity. These stimuli can be divided into sensory stimuli, i.e. tactile, olfactory, visual and auditory stimuli, on the one hand and seminal plasma-related stimuli on the other (Langendijk et al., 2005). The presence of a boar during AI stimulated the estrus signs expression (Kemp et al., 2005) and endogenous release of oxytocin and enhanced uterine contractions (Langendijk et al., 2003; Willenburg et al., 2003; Langendijk et al., 2005; Umesiobi, 2010). Further more, whole boar semen or seminal plasma has been demonstrated to advance the time of ovulation in gilts and sows (Waberski et al., 2006). Namely, the boar ejaculate contains high levels of estrogens (Claus, 1990), which stimulates myometrial contractions (Willenburg et al., 2004) via an estrogen-induced local release of prostaglandin F₂ α (Claus, 1990; Willenburg et al., 2004). The synchronization of viable spermatozoa presence in oviduct and the time of ovulation is ofextremely importance for successful fertilization. It is plausible that semen-induced cytokines in the uterine lymph undergo counter-current transfer to the ipsilateral ovary and accelerate the final maturation of pre-ovulatory follicles (O'Leary et al., 2004; Waberski et al., 2006). Releasing the endogenous oxytocin and myometrial contraction can also be induced with cervix stimulation by moving catheter within the cervix, immediately before and after AI dose deposition (Fülöp et al., 1992; Steverink et

al., 1998; Grafenau et al., 2005; Stančić et al., 2006). It has been demonstrated (Stančić et al., 2006) that cervix stimulation by catheter immediately before and after insemination, significantly increase farrowing rate (83.3%) and liveborn biglets per litter (10,1), compared with unstimulated sows (Farrowing rate = 71.1%; liveborn piglets = 9.33).

CONCLUSION

Cervix stimulation, immediately before and after sperm deposition or sow stimulation with boar presence immediately around AI, significantly increase farrowing rate (90% and 86%) compared with untreated sows (78%). Subsequent litter sizes were not affected by treatment.

However, according to results of other authors, this method is controversial and the generalized recommendations for use should be made with caution, since the most profound effects occur in sub-fertile farms, groups of sows, seasonal infertility, and with sub-fertile boars. However, in many cases, farrowing rate and litter size are improved.

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UTICAJ STIMULACIJA CERVIKSA I PRISUSTVO NERASTA PRILIKOM VEŠTAČKOG OSEMENJAVANJA NA FERTILITET KRMAČA

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Izvod

U radu je izvršeno poređenje vrednosti prašenja i veličine legla kod krmača veštački osemenjanih posle stimulacije cerviksa ili stimulisanih prisustvom nerasta neposredno oko osemenjavanja. Unutar 7 dana posle zaučenja, ukupno 149 krmača je

podeljeno u tri grupe. Grupa I: stimulacija cerviksa kateterom, neposredno pre i posle depozicije sperme (n=49), Grupa II: stimulacija krmača prisustvom nerasta neposredno pre, tokom i posle inseminacije (n=50) i Grupa III: kontrolne, nestimulisane, krmače (n=50). Vrednost prašenja je bila značajno veća ($P < 0.05$) posle stimulacije cerviksa (90%) i prisustva nerasta (86%) u poređenju sa nestimulisanim krmačama (78%). Ova vrednost se nije značajno razlikovala ($P > 0.05$) između stimulisanih grupa krmača (grupe I i II). Izvedeni tretmani stimulacije nisu značajno uticali na veličinu legla. Ovi rezultati pokazuju da stimulacija cerviksa ili prisustvo nerasta neposredno oko osemenjavanja, mogu biti korisne metode povećanja fertiliteta krmača.

Ključne reči: cerviks, prisustvo nerasta, stimulacija, aktivnost miometriuma, fertilitet, krmača.

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